

Abstract:

This article discusses the main directions and methods for cultivating a positive attitude toward the environment in primary school students, as well as the pedagogical strategies implemented to achieve this goal.

Keywords: ecology, biosphere, method, ecological attitude, environment, technique, approach, ecological education, ecological upbringing, technology.

Introduction

It is noteworthy that many preschool educational institutions in our country organize classes to introduce children to nature and the environment. As President Shavkat Mirziyoyev stated, “The most important issue is to seriously consider increasing the ecological awareness of the population. Of course, such problems cannot be solved solely through administrative means; they must be addressed by nurturing love and a sense of belonging to nature in the hearts of the younger generation.” Accordingly, 70% of preschool institutions in our country have special rooms for ecological education, and 16% have “Environmental Trails” where children learn to care for nature. In Uzbekistan, environmental topics are covered in the subjects “The World Around Us” for grades 1 and 2 and “Man and Nature” for grades 3 and 4 in all primary schools. This demonstrates that attention and love for the environment are instilled from an early age.

The main direction in fostering a positive attitude toward the environment in primary school students lies in the transition from concrete-imaginative thinking to abstract-logical thinking. This process initially occurs at the sensory stage of cognition, where children form perceptions of the environment through their five senses. Various forms of thinking play a key role in this development, such as classification, comparison, analogy, synthesis, abstraction, generalization, and systematization.

Unfortunately, today we are so absorbed in our daily routines that we fail to perceive the irreversible damage being inflicted on both living and non-living nature by human activity. Therefore, a strong connection between education and upbringing must be established from childhood. This makes it crucial to instill the foundations of ecological education in children's minds even before school age. The word “ecology” originates from the Greek words “oikos” (home) and “logos” (study), and it refers to the science that studies the relationship between living organisms and their environment, as well as interactions within the biosphere.

Children are first attracted to nature through its beauty, bright colors, and diversity. As such, ecological education must be approached with varying content, forms, methods, and strategies throughout different stages of life—from preschool and school years to community life, work environments, and old age. The first concrete knowledge and experiences children gain are drawn from nature itself.

The more diverse and rich the techniques used to foster a positive attitude toward the environment, the more successfully the educational goals will be achieved. According to N.J. Isakulova, the following are important didactic functions in the process of interdisciplinary ecological education:

- Using supplementary tasks such as ecological exercises, problem-solving, dictations, and compositions;
- Integrating ecological content into lessons through a variety of interdisciplinary methods;
- Conducting extracurricular activities based on students' different interests and using varied strategies;
- Ensuring content diversity in ecological quizzes and question-answer formats;
- Considering different forms of evaluating students' knowledge, skills, and competencies in ecological education.

There are four main methods of forming an environmental perspective and implementing children's activities:

1. **Visual Methods** (observation, demonstration, inspection): These are effective ways to gather accurate information about plants, animals, and natural phenomena. Children not only perceive external parameters such as color, texture, smell, and shape but also learn about their environmental relationships.
2. **Verbal Methods** (conversation, storytelling, reading literature): These help children form comprehensive ideas about the environment. Techniques include explanation, instruction, pedagogical assessment, and questioning—e.g., composing stories about houseplants or pets.
3. **Practical Methods**: These include exercises, experiments, modeling, and practical tasks based on children's experiences and problem-solving.
4. **Play Methods**: These include didactic games about the environment, role-play with toys, imitative actions, hide-and-seek games, outdoor games, episodic game techniques, and riddles.

Environmental projects also play a significant role in shaping a positive attitude toward the environment in primary school students. These projects integrate all types of children's activities and educational fields, aligning them with state and societal requirements. As noted, "Uzbekistan possesses rich natural resources and powerful economic and human potential. However, our greatest wealth is the enormous intellectual and spiritual capacity of our people."

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